

PCL-HYDROXYAPATITE COMPOSITE SCAFFOLDS FOR BONE REGENERATION

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SUMMARY

Scaffolds are used in tissue engineering as a physical support for tissue regeneration. Polymer-ceramic composites may be useful for bone regeneration. Here we used poly(ϵ -caprolactone), together with hydroxyapatite, in order to obtain scaffolds with enhanced mechanical properties and bioactivity, and enhanced bioactivity by surface modifications.

Keywords: poly(ϵ -caprolactone); hydroxyapatite; tissue engineering; mechanical properties; bioactivity

INTRODUCTION

Scaffolds are used in tissue engineering as a physical and biological support for seeding cells, and transplant them into the organism. In the field of bone tissue engineering, polymer matrix/ceramic load composites have been pointed out as promising materials for tissue scaffolding, well they may combine both the advantages of polymer materials and ceramics. Various studies have shown improved biocompatibility and higher expression of osteogenic markers when HAp[1],[2], [3] or Bioglass is incorporated to biocompatible polymers like PCL, PLA or PLGA. This behaviour may be partially explained by an improved adsorption of binding ECM proteins, such as Fibronectin or Vibronectin, to composites respect to neat polymers [4]. Besides, a biomimetic technique consisting in the deposition of bone-like apatite onto polymeric scaffolds in simulated body fluid has been developed, based on the works of Kokubo. His group first described the composition of a solution called simulated body fluid, (later on SBF), able to reproduce in vitro changes that normally occur when a bioactive material is implanted in the body prior to bone bonding, namely the deposition of an apatite layer on the surface of the material. The apatite formed is known to be carbonated, moderately crystalline, and to contain substitution atoms like Mg and Na; thus it is more similar to bone apatite than synthetic ones (highly pure and crystalline), being thus generally described as biomimetic or bonelike apatite [5],[6]. Based on the assumption that biomimetic coated materials would show a better cellular response as uncoated ones, SBF-coating or synthesis of biomimetic apatite-polymer [7] hybrid materials has been approached as a strategy *per se*, not for assessing in vitro bioactivity, but aiming to obtain better biological properties; the inclusion of proteins during coating has been considered as well [8],[9], and even the synthesis of apatite by a chemical way using SBF as a reaction medium[10], [11])

In this work, we synthesized interconnected porous scaffolds of poly(ϵ -caprolactone) and poly(ϵ -caprolactone)-hydroxyapatite composites by a mixed porogen leaching/phase inversion process. We then used a treatment for promoting apatite bonding ability [12] and subjected the scaffolds to SBF immersion; untreated samples were used as well in order to compare the obtained results. Scaffolds were then characterized by mean of microscopy, elemental analysis, thermogravimetry, and the effect of HAp coating on mechanical properties was evaluated with compression tests.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of the scaffolds

PCL Mn=50000, PDI= was furnished by Polysciences. HAp particles of mean size 90 nm were a courtesy from the Centre for Biomaterials of la Habana, Cuba. 1,4-dioxane and ethanol of purity 98% were bought from Scharlab and used as received. The sheets of neat PCL were prepared by melting PCL pellets between two glass plates at 90°C during 20 min and subsequent cooling in air. Scaffolds were prepared by a mixed particle leaching/freeze extraction process. PEMA beads (Lucite International) with mean diameter 200 microns were used as a porogen. Freeze extraction is a modification of freeze drying as proposed by Wang and al [13]. In our case, dioxane was used as a solvent, and it was dissolved in the freezer at -20°C in ethanol.

First the hydroxyapatite nanoparticles were dispersed in dioxane by ultrasonic exposure. Then polycaprolactone was added and dissolved under constant stirring. The ratio PCL/dioxane was 17.6% by weight in all the scaffolds. The nanoparticle content in the composites was 2,5, 7.5 or 15% by weight with respect to PCL, nanocomposite samples will be designed as PCL2.5HAp, PCL7.5HAp, PCL15HAp respectively. The solution was mixed with PEMA beads in a weight ratio 4/5 and immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen. Solvent extraction was performed in cold ethanol at -10°C as described in [13]; ethanol was changed three times. Subsequently particle leaching was performed in ethanol at 40°C.

Biomimetic HAp deposition

A series of nanocomposite scaffolds was treated following the procedure described in [12]. Samples that were subjected to this treatment are thereafter designed as treated samples. Control scaffolds were immersed directly in SBF without nucleating treatment to verify the influence of the treatment on apatite-nucleating ability. Subsequently the scaffolds were immersed in simulated body fluid, SBF, with the following molar concentrations: Na⁺ 142.0; K⁺ 5.0; Mg²⁺ 1.5; Ca²⁺ 2.5; Cl⁻ 148.8; HCO₃⁻ 4.2 ; HPO₄²⁻ 2-1.0; SO₄²⁻ 0,5 buffered at pH 7,4 with Tris hydroxymethylaminomethane (0,5M) and hydrochloric acid (1M), prepared as described in [14]. The SBF was changed weekly in order to replace the precipitated ionic species and ensure a nearly constant ionic activity. A second group of samples used for mechanical testing was treated with the mentioned treatment and immersed in SBFx2 (twice the mentioned ionic concentrations) for two weeks to accelerate the mineralization process as described by Kim et al. [15]. The SBF was changed weekly as in the first series.

Porosity measurement: Porosity was measured by gravimetric means. The samples were weighed dry, filled with ethanol under vacuum, and subsequently weighed again.

Porosity was calculated as the quotient of the volume of pores and the total volume of the scaffold [16].

SEM observation and elemental analysis: Samples were observed with a JEOL JSM6300 scanning electron microscope with an acceleration tension of 10kV. Energy dispersive X-ray analysis, EDX, was performed in order to analyze the quantitative composition of the deposited mineral.

Fourier Transform IR Analysis: Chemical surface changes with nucleation treatment were studied using an FTIR Thermo Nicolet Nexus apparatus in ATR mode. Surfaces of untreated, sodium hydroxide treated, and apatite covered samples were measured.

Contact angle measurement: Contact angle measurement with water was performed by sessile drop method, using a Dataphysics OCA20 device equipped with a Nikon Camera; contact angles were calculated using image analysis software. Results were averaged from a set of at least five drops.

TGA measurements: Thermogravimetric analysis (SDTQ600 TA Instruments) was used in order to determine the quantity of HAp nanoparticles and deposited HAp in the samples. Samples were subjected to a temperature ramp from room temperature until 700°C, at 20°C/min under nitrogen flow (50mL/min).

Mechanical analysis: Samples were cut into pieces of 5x5x3 mm approximately, and compressed in a Microtest standard compression machine with a 15N load cell. Presented results are mean values of at least 5 measurements. Statistical analysis was used to compare results of diverse scaffold types: a t-test was used and differences were considered significant for $p < 0,05$.

RESULTS

Structure of the scaffolds

As can be seen on figure 1, scaffolds show double pore structure owing to the fabrication process. Porogen leaching leads to an interconnected macroporous structure with pores of around 200-300 microns connected by large throats, whereas solvent crystallization and subsequent dissolution leads to microporosity with micrometric channelled structure (insets). Porosity of the scaffolds reached 85 ± 1.7 %; porosity of pure PCL scaffold was slightly higher than porosity of composite scaffolds but as can be seen in SEM pictures, overall structure was not affected by HAp nanoparticles incorporation. As can be seen in the SEM micrographs taken at higher magnification (insets in fig. 1), many HAp nanoparticles appear on the inner surfaces of the scaffolds.

Figure 1. Composite scaffolds synthesized by mixed freeze-extraction process: pure PCL (a); PCL with 2,5% HAp (b); PCL with 7,5% HAp (c); PCL with 15% HAp (d) and detail of the microstructure (insets: dimension bar 10 μ m)

Surface Analysis of bulk samples

In order to deposit a layer of biomimetic hydroxyapatite on the internal surface of the porous structure of the scaffold, it was subjected to different treatments to facilitate the nucleation of the HAp crystals on the surface. Characterizing the effect of such treatments on the bended surface of the scaffold trabeculae is not easy, thus, flat sheets of neat PCL were subjected to the same treatments to characterize the change induced in the surface properties.

Wettability was greatly enhanced by surface treatment with sodium hydroxide, as can (contact angle with water changed from $72,5\pm 0,5$ to 37 ± 1 upon etching with sodium hydroxide). Biomimetic apatite coating did not show any further decisive effect on wettability.

Figure 2a. Change of C-O/C-O-C ratio in the spectra of PCL solvent cast films after etching one day (PCL-e1) and two days (PCL-e2) with molar sodium hydroxide. 2b.

FTIR-ATR spectrum of untreated (PCL) and apatite-covered PCL film (PCL-c): phosphate group (◇), carbonate group (☆) and groups from polymer moieties (○)

Analysis of the sample surface with FTIR after etching with sodium hydroxide treatment showed an increased proportion of C-O bonds with respect to ester bonds (Figure 2a). The effect increased with longer treatment times. Results of FTIR can explain the increase in wettability with water observed by sessile drop measurement by the increase of polar groups respect to aliphatic backbone due to chain scission. After coating with the apatite layer (figure 2b), the characteristic peaks for PCL disappear, and phosphate associated peaks are to see: at 964 the ν_1 mode of phosphate, and in the range between $970-1135\text{ cm}^{-1}$ the ν_3 stretching mode, as well as weak peaks associated with CO_3^{2-} at $1460, 1420$ and 875 cm^{-1} , (characteristic for B-type substitution, where

CO_3^{2-} substitutes phosphate moieties). Nonetheless, the strong peaks at $1695\text{-}1735\text{ cm}^{-1}$ associated with carbonyl stretching, or the peaks at $2800\text{-}3000$ typical for CH_2 symmetrical and antisymmetrical stretching of the PCL backbone do not appear.

Deposition of biomimetic apatite on PCL scaffolds

Apatite was successfully deposited on PCL after nucleation treatment by immersion in alternate Ca / PO_4 solutions and as can be seen on micrographs of figure 3. The EDX analysis of the deposited apatite layer shows the presence of impurities such as potassium, chlorine and magnesium, which is common for biomimetic apatite. The nucleating effect of synthetic HAp nanoparticles seems to increase with the quantity present on the surface, well PCL15HAp showed the most apatite formation, with a dense layer of cauliflower shaped crystals covering all the structure (figure 4).

Figure 3: Evolution of mineral layer deposition after SBF immersion of untreated samples during one (a), two (b) or three (c) weeks for neat PCL (left) and PCL15HAp (right). (bar size $30\mu\text{m}$ excepted PCL15HAp (a), $60\mu\text{m}$)

Figure 4: Mineral layer formation after nucleation treatment in neat PCL and composite PCL-HAp scaffolds after several weeks immersion in SBF

Quantitative results of element proportions in the deposited mineral layer are listed in Table 1. The ratios of Ca/P and Cl/P are represented as an indicator for specificity of the deposition. A bone-like hydroxyapatite layer should present a Ca/P ratio close to 1.65 that is the value reported for bone. High chlorine ions content should indicate undifferentiated precipitation and is not indicative for bone bonding ability.

Table 1. Atomic Ca/P and Cl/P ratios measured from EDX element analysis

		ratio Ca/P	ratio Cl/P
Control group (without treatment)	pure PCL	2,3	3,4
	2,5 HAp	3,4	3,1
	7,5 HAp	2,7	3,5
	15 HAp	3,4	0,5
Nucleation treatment	pure PCL	2,3	0,1
	2,5 HAp	1,3	0,5
	7,5 HAp	1,6	0,2
	15 HAp	1,6	0,4

The total amount of mineral deposited in the nucleated scaffolds was measured with TGA as a function of the immersion time in SBF (Figure 5). Surprisingly, the pure PCL sample reached the greatest deposition rate, above that of samples containing 2,5% and 7,5% HAp, and with a deposited apatite content at week 3 comparable with that of 15% HAp sample. The trend for mineral deposition rate varies from sample to sample, being almost linear for treated 15HAp, 7,5HAp and 2,5HAp samples, and square root shaped for treated pure PCL.

Figure 5. Deposited mineral, in weight percent, on the treated scaffolds surfaces after immersion in SBF for different times, calculated by the residual weight after calcinations at 700°C: pure PCL (◆), PCL with 2,5% HAp (▲), PCL with 7,5% HAp (□), PCL with 15% HAp (●)

Hybrid structure

Amazingly, we discovered that treated samples that had been coated for two or three weeks in SBF, showed after calcination at 700°C in nitrogen atmosphere in the TGA (figure 6), a residue that conserved the initial shape of the scaffold (also when not showing much mechanical resistance and crumbling when held with a clamp). Figure 6 shows a micrograph of the TGA residue of a 15HAp treated scaffold after 3 weeks in SBF.

Figure 6. Micrograph of the pyrolysis residue of a PCL 15 composite treated with nucleation treatment and covered with biomimetic apatite for three weeks in SBF. Bar size 400 μm

Mechanical testing

The results of the compression tests for the uncoated and coated samples are presented in Figure . Between untreated samples, the incorporation of HAp nanoparticles is seen to have a strengthening effect on the elastic modulus as well as on the yield stress of the scaffolds. In the case of the pure PCL scaffold and also in the composite scaffold containing 15% HAp nanoparticles both the elastic modulus and yield stress (data not

shown) are seen to be significantly higher in the scaffolds coated with biomimetic HAp than in the uncoated ones, whereas the difference is not significant for PCL 7,5%HAp and PCL 2,5%HAp samples.

Figure 7. Evolution of Young modulus after apatite deposition on scaffolds. (* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$)

DISCUSSION

Hydroxyapatite coating formation

Much has been written about apatite layer formation on materials in simulated body fluid. A qualitative assessment of basic properties of the mineral phase, as may be atomic composition, Ca/P ratio, crystal morphology and crystallinity, is necessary. This aspect is fundamental when reported to biological properties, yet cells react very differently depending, for example, on coating crystallinity: amorphous calcium phosphate has been shown to provoke cytotoxicity in vitro and in vivo, likely because of high concentrations of both calcium and phosphates. Here, the coatings described have been characterized with SEM and elemental analysis, revealing that all the expectable elements are contained and pointing toward calcium phosphates being deposited. The nucleation of mineral phase is highly enhanced by the presence of hydroxyapatite particles, as can be seen on the micrographs from figure 3. Whereas pure PCL show scarce nuclei with typical pre-apatite shape [17], PCL15HAp shows dense coating with cauliflower structure as usually described for apatite; this is the confirmation that hydroxyapatite introduction into PCL matrix causes an improved biocompatibility of the scaffold.

Besides, the effect of the nucleation treatment is positive regarding to amount of apatite deposited and speed of deposition, chloride precipitation, as well as regarding to Ca/P ratios of the mineral layer. From the FTIR measurements it can be seen that the apatite deposited is carbonated, likely with a B-substitution type (location of the associated peaks at 1460, 1420 and 875 cm^{-1}), as is usually observed when a SBF with a hydrogenocarbonate content lower than 20 mM is used [18]) when carbonate substitutes to phosphate.

Interpenetrated hybrid structure and mechanical strengthening

Resulting from biomimetic apatite growth in the scaffold, an interpenetrated hybrid structure with two co-continuous phases was generated by long time-treatments, as is patent from figure 6. Figure 6 shows that a high interpenetration is reached well the physical macrostructure remains when burning out the organic part of the scaffold. This was observed with samples that were mineralized during three weeks, and we then designed another experiment for assessing the mechanical strengthening that can be obtained by the apatite layer deposition. As explained in the results section, strengthening was effective in half of the cases considered at a statistically significant level. Albeit we do not believe that scaffolds should be used as implants with this degree of mineralization, well according to the results by Chim et al [19] in vivo results may be compromised by a flaking of the mineral layer under physiological stresses. Nevertheless, these results are interesting well in vivo mineralization should be able to produce the same type of structure through secretion of extracellular matrix proteins and mineralization of this matrix, thus permitting a strengthening of the construct and a good interaction between colonizing tissue and scaffold.

CONCLUSION

We were able to synthesize materials with highly interconnected macroporosity very alike to the trabeculae of spongy bone, with suitable pore size for trabeculae formation and vascularization; once treated, these materials show rapid apatite formation in SBF (clue for bone bonding), and they possess a high specific surface that is thought to enhance surface reactivity; at least, these materials enjoy the well-known biocompatible and bioactive character of PCL-HAp biomaterials; they may be able to rapid strengthening when implanted due to interpenetration with ECM and mineralization, as demonstrated by mechanical testing after in vitro biomineralization. These are many clues leading to think that these composite scaffolds should be a promising basis for bone tissue engineering.

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